

Grant Agreement 101079792, RESILIENCE PPP

Quality Assessment Plan

Title of Deliverable:	Quality Assessment Plan (QAP)	
Deliverable Number:	6.4	
Type of Data:	Report	
Lead Beneficiary:	FSCIRE	
Publishing Status:	Public	
Last Revision Date:	22/05/2023	by: Francesca Cadeddu
Verification Date:	30/05/2023	by: Project Coordinator
Approval Date:	30/05/2023	by: Board of Executive Directors
Document Name:	RESILIENCE_WP6_QualityAssessmentPlan_01.00_FINAL	

Change History

Version No.	Date	Status	Name	Summary of Main Changes
00.01	17/01/2023	DRAFT	Initial Draft	
00.02	22/05/2023	DRAFT	Second draft	Additions and amendments according to WP leaders' feedback
01.00	30/05/2023	FINAL	Final version	Feedback WP leaders and BoD

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
DOP	Detailed Organisational Plan
BoD	Board of Directors
CDEP	Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan
CDE	Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation
DMP	Data Management Plan
ED	Executive Director
GA	Grant Agreement
GenA	General Assembly
M	Month
PC	Project Coordinator
PP	Preparatory Phase
PPP	Preparatory Phase Project
REA	European Research Executive Agency
RI	Research Infrastructure
SSC	Service Coordination Committee
TM	Team Member(s)
TNA	Trans-National Access
WP	Work Package
WU	Work Unit

1 Document overview

1.1 Objectives

This document is the Quality Assessment Plan (QAP) for the Grant Agreement (GA) n. 101079792, signed by European Research Executive Agency (REA) and the RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase Project (PPP) consortium. It represents the reference document by which RESILIENCE demonstrates that it:

- understands the project, risks, outcomes and outputs of its work packages (WPs) and work units (WUs);
- has defined the deliverables, the related roles and responsibilities, the processes to follow, their quality assurance (extent and format of checks and reviews);
- has identified the processes and tools which guarantee to its main activities and outcomes an appropriate level of quality;
- has identified the major risks and the corresponding preventive actions.
- postulates the project's key performance indicators;
- defines the procedures to make an efficient use of both internal and external feedback to ensure the continuous improvement of the project.

At the end of the Preparatory Phase, the RESILIENCE PPP consortium will evaluate the effectiveness of the present document and, in case of a positive outcome, adopt it as the QAP for the RESILIENCE RI.

1.2 Scope

This QAP covers the activities foreseen for the RESILIENCE PPP organisational bodies as they are described in the D8.1 RESILIENCE Governance, HR Policy and management and Access Policy (RESILIENCE 2YSEP GA n. 871127) and the RESILIENCE PPP DESCA.

This QAP is to be applied by each staff working in the project and to all work performed within it. It is a document on which the partners express agreement and to which they are committed.

In case of misinterpretation or conflicts, the Grant Agreement Contract and its annexes have precedence over this document.

2 The project

The European Research Executive Agency (REA) signed a Grant Agreement (GA) with the RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase Project (PPP) consortium. The main aim of the RESILIENCE PPP is to bring RESILIENCE, a European Research Infrastructure on Religious Studies, to the completion of its Preparatory Phase, which started in 2021 and will end in 2025. The work includes legal, governance, financial, technical, strategic, and administrative aspects carried out in 6 work packages. The primary outcomes of the PPP are the setting-up of the legal and financial frameworks of the functioning of the RI; the preparation of signature-ready documents towards the implementation phase; the completion of the RESILIENCE service catalogue, and the establishment of legal agreements and technical frameworks for their operation.

RESILIENCE (Religious Studies Infrastructure: tooLs, Innovation, Experts, conNectiions and Centres in Europe) is a distributed Research Infrastructure that entered the ESFRI Roadmap in 2021. Its mission is to address the challenge of creating a larger, structured involvement of excellent scholars who innovatively produce competencies, knowledge, approaches, and impact within the scientific domain of Religious Studies.

The aims, contents, actions and organizational structure of RESILIENCE PPP are described in the Grant Agreement n. 101079792, in D8.1 RESILIENCE Governance, HR Policy and management and Access Policy (RESILIENCE 2YSEP GA n. 871127), in D6.1 Governance set-up proceedings (RESILIENCE PPP GA n. 101079792), which is a public document available on the RESILIENCE website and the Consortium agreement based on the DESCA – Model Consortium Agreement for Horizon Europe, version 1, December 2021.

2.1 Risks

The Risks foreseen for the RESILIENCE PPP and the proposed mitigation measures are the following:

Description of risk (indicate level of (i) likelihood, and (ii) severity: Low/Medium/High)	Work package(s) involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Actual costs exceed budgeted costs [Likelihood: Low] [Severity: High]	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	Strict monitoring of costs with respect to progress Request extra inkind effort from partners Increase national co-funding with respect to that of EU
Poor political and Financial Support [Likelihood: Medium] [Severity: Medium]	WP1	Collective support activities to optimise the performance of the teams in achieving to collect national supports Mutualise the lessons learned and best practices
Delays in issuing project deliverables [Likelihood: Medium] [Severity: Medium]	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5	Adopt Agile methods for faster adaptability Implement early warning mechanism. Monthly progress review

Loss of digital data [Likelihood: Low] [Severity: High]	WP2, WP3	Use fault-tolerant cloud services (ie CINECA) Store digital data in storages hosted in separate locations Sensitive data are subject to version control and back-up policy. Passwords to have access to key data are stored in secured shared password wallets.
Unavailability of personnel [Likelihood: High] [Severity: Medium]	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	Identification of key personnel Each key person has a backup trained for cases of staff replacement
Physical gatherings not possible [Likelihood: High] [Severity: Medium]	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	Replace physical attendances by videoconferencing Invest into digital/remote working paradigm hardware and software
Conflict among RESILIENCE partners [Likelihood: Medium] [Severity: Low]	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	Escalation path through project entities to treat project issues Implement measures of early warning. Divert activities to partners able to implement them. Pressure on partner (i.e.: costs transfers) if recurrent problems.
Resignation of a partner [Likelihood: Medium] [Severity: Medium]	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	Implement a policy of finding high potential new partners Regular meetings with partners to assess, among others, the motivation Include a shadow phase between the replacement partner and the leaving partner to minimise disruption of activities.

3 The deliverables

The GA n. 101079792 enlists the following deliverables:

WP No	Deliv. Related No	Deliv. No	Deliverable Name	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemin. Level	Due Date
WP1	D1.1	D1	RESILIENCE ERIC Statutes, bylaws and protocols – 1 st draft	The deliverable collects all documents requested for the establishment of the ERIC in their first version	FSCIRE	R	PU	30 Nov 2024
WP1	D1.2	D2	RESILIENCE ERIC Statutes bylaws and protocols – last version	The deliverable collects all documents requested for the establishment of the ERIC in their latest version before the signature of the Member Countries.	FSCIRE	R	PU	30 Nov 2025
WP1	D1.3	D3	Financial Sustainability Plan	The deliverable presents the Business Model and Financial Plan for the later stages of the Preparatory Phase and the Implementation Phase, and the transition from one to the other.	FSCIRE	R	PU	31 May 2024
WP2	D2.1	D4	Services Preparation and Implementation Strategy	Detailed description of the strategy for implementing RESILIENCE services	FSCIRE	R	PU	31 Jul 2025
WP2	D2.2	D5	User Services Catalogue	Organised, curated and documented collection of any and all user services that can be performed on the RESILIENCE platform.	KU Leuven	R	PU	30 Nov 2025
WP2	D2.3	D6	IT Services Catalogue	Organised, curated and documented collection of any and all IT services supporting the user services operated on the RESILIENCE platform.	FSCIRE	R	PU	30 Apr 2026
WP2	D2.4	D7	Data Management Plan	Plan detailing how to make data FAIR, including what data RESILIENCE manages, whether and how it is made accessible for verification and re-use, and how it will be curated and preserved.	KU Leuven	DMP	PU	30 Sep 2025
WP2	D2.5	D8	TNA Services Management Plan	The TNA Management Plan describes criteria of excellence for TNA hosts and users, their rights and duties within the program, quality monitoring procedures and responsibilities (incl. Peer Review Committee), and efficient information providing and research enhancing workflows.	KU Leuven	R	PU	31 Oct 2025
WP2	D2.6	D9	Training Services Management Plan	The Training Management Plan defines the model of training activities provided by RESILIENCE and represents a guide for the partners involved in training activities.	TUA	R	PU	31 Jul 2025

WP No	Deliv. Related No	Deliv. No	Deliverable Name	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemin. Level	Due Date
WP2	D2.7	D13	Security Management Plan (SMP)	The Security Management Plan is elaborated to define all aspects of the working practices of the project to guarantee secure delivery. It contains a Secure Coding/Development Guidelines aligned with "ISO/IEC 27034 Information technology – Security techniques", the OWASP Developer Guide, Testing Guide and Top-10 Application Security Risks	FSCIRE	R	PU	30 Nov 2023
WP2	D2.8	D14	Software Development Plan Template (SDPT)	The Software Development Plan Template is elaborated to define all best practices for the development, testing and installation of a software to be created and maintained within the context of RESILIENCE. The SDPT is foundational for the IT aspect of RESILIENCE, since each software project will then create an instance of this template specifically adapted to the software maintained	KU Leuven	R	PU	30 Nov 2023
WP2	D2.9	D15	Data Centre Services – Services Level Requirements (SLR)	Collection of the project services requirements from all management team members. This information, a mandatory ITIL deliverable will be presented as Service Level Requirements (SLR) and is an important deliverable that must be clearly defined, documented, signed off, and understood by all project stakeholders before the Data Centre Services service could be delivered.	FSCIRE	R	PU	31 May 2024
WP2	D2.10	D16	Operation Management Policy (OMP)	From the DCS-SLR, the team will create an Operations Management Policy that will contain operation guidelines and responsibilities, service level arrangements and delivery conditions.	KU Leuven	R	PU	31 May 2025

WP No	Deliv. Related No	Deliv. No	Deliverable Name	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemin. Level	Due Date
WP2	D2.11	D17	Master/Reference Data Management (MDM)	For all services to be aligned with researchers' needs in terms of data exchange, RESILIENCE needs to establish a Reference Data Architecture as well as the processes to maintain it during the whole RI duration. Our deliverable will be developed upon 2 levels of abstraction: - Data Level: Aligned with Master Data management, a common RESILIENCE Data dictionary is developed that covers all Religious Studies Research information systems. This allows all WPs applications to exchange information transparently. - Service Level: One step above, at service level, a common definition language is created in order to interoperate between systems with common semantic and structured language rules.	KU Leuven	R	PU	31 May 2025
WP2	D2.12	D18	TNA – Management Report (TNA-MR)	This deliverable will present the results of the pilot TNA activities, evaluating the results, difficulties and potential risks and opportunities.	KU Leuven	R	PU	30 Apr 2026
WP2	D2.13	D19	Trainings – Management Report (T-MR)	This deliverable presents the results of the pilot training activities, evaluating the results, difficulties and potential risks and opportunities.	TUA	R	PU	30 Apr 2026
WP3	D3.1	D10	Workshops proceedings – 1 st batch	Collection of notes and media documents presenting the highlights of all Design Thinking workshops.	WWU	R	PU	29 Feb 2024
WP3	D3.2	D20	Workshop Proceedings – 2 nd batch	Collection of notes and media documents presenting the highlights of all Design Thinking workshops.	WWU	R	PU	30 Nov 2025
WP3	D3.3	D21	Documented Use Cases – 1 st batch	for each service, user/functional requirements are documented using use cases and collected within D3.1, including a set of S.M.A.R.T. objectives for the next project phase.	WWU	R	PU	31 Mar 2024
WP3	D3.4	D22	Documented Use Cases – 2 nd batch	For each service, user/functional requirements are documented using use cases and collected within D3.2, including a set of S.M.A.R.T. objectives for the next project phase	WWU	R	PU	30 Nov 2025
WP3	D3.5	D23	User Stories Catalogue – 1 st batch	Collections of User Stories allowing to identify roles connected with services functions	WWU	R	PU	31 Oct 2023

WP No	Deliv. Related No	Deliv. No	Deliverable Name	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemin. Level	Due Date
WP3	D3.6	D24	User Stories Catalogue – 2 nd batch	Collections of User Stories allowing to identify roles connected with services functions	WWU	R	PU	30 Nov 2024
WP4	D4.1	D11	Communication&Dissemination Plan – RESILIENCE PPP	The plan adapts C&D strategies to the developing structure of RESILIENCE, ensuring a sound coordination on what, how, when and to whom is communicated by the partners, and to be ready for the Implementation Phase	TUA	R	PU	31 Oct 2022
WP4	D4.2	D25	Communication and Dissemination Plan – RESILIENCE PPP, 2 nd version	The plan updates C&D strategies identified in D4.1 to the developing structure of RESILIENCE, ensuring a sound coordination on what, how, when and to whom is communicated by the partners, and to make a first balance of the strategy chosen and applied.	TUA	R	PU	30 Nov 2024
WP4	D4.3	D26	Communication and Dissemination Plan – RESILIENCE PPP, Looking forward	The plan updates C&D strategies identified in D4.1 to the developing structure of RESILIENCE, ensuring a sound coordination on what, how, when and to whom is communicated by the partners, and be ready for the Implementation Phase	TUA	R	PU	31 Jan 2026
WP4	D4.4	D27	Report on Study of the subset of services	The report details the input, activities, output and outcomes of the study conducted.	UNISOFIA	R	PU	31 Aug 2023
WP5	D5.1	D12	Impact analysis	The document reports on the measures of the RESILIENCE impact, the methodology chosen to identify and measure them according to the RESILIENCE impact areas and on the geographic areas where RESILIENCE hubs and nodes are present.	UNSA	R	PU	30 Nov 2025
WP6	D6.1	D28	Governance set-up proceedings	GenA, BoD and WU members meet at the kick-off of the project, share and synchronise working rules. The calendar of meetings is adopted and made public.	FSCIRE	R	PU	30 Jun 2022
WP6	D6.2	D29	Templates and guidelines for the monitoring, reporting and management activities	Documents for financial, effort, and reporting monitoring are produced, shared among and explained to partners to support the project performance	FSCIRE	R	PU	31 Aug 2022
WP6	D6.3	D30	Detailed Organisational Plan (DOP)	The plan provides the tools for the management activities and also templates supporting the reporting activity.	FSCIRE	R	PU	31 Oct 2022
WP6	D6.4	D31	Quality Assessment Plan (QAP)	The plan details the Quality Management system adopted by RESILIENCE, including the processes for quality management and assessment, risks analysis, performance indicators management and a strategy to deal with ethics.	FSCIRE	R	PU	30 Sep 2022

In addition, the teams and individuals working in the RESILIENCE PPP may need or have to prepare and deliver documents and/or other objects which are useful for the project’s development and evidence of the work conducted.

3.1 Roles and responsibilities

All deliverables involve the following roles, with the enlisted responsibilities:

Roles	Responsibilities
Project Coordinator	<p>For the GA n. 101079792 deliverables only, the PC is responsible for establishing the proper deliverable management system and follow-up, and for verifying that the deliverables meet the quality requirements and the consistency expected by REA.</p> <p>For all other deliverables, the PC supports, upon requests, their development.</p>
Author	<p>Individuals with the scientific/technical/managerial knowledge to define the contents of a given deliverable. If several authors contribute to a single deliverable, one author is identified as the main author to ensure good communication and coordination.</p> <p>The author’s responsibilities are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To prepare the structure and contents of the deliverable; ● To submit the deliverable for review at the appropriate level, and verify subsequent updates resulting there from; ● To ensure consistency between deliverable contents, the GA, and the current baseline; ● To lay out the deliverable in accordance with the standards defined by the QAP; ● To send deliverables for review to reviewers, as defined in section 3.2.2 below; ● To observe the indications concerning the preparation, management and storage of files offered by the RESILIENCE PPP Data Management Plan and D6.2 Templates and guidelines for the monitoring, reporting and management activities; ● To communicate to WP4 the news regarding the delivery and support the drafting of text related to it. ● To send deliverables to the Project Coordinator (PC) for submission to the REA through the EC web portal (if applicable) <p>When the deliverable takes a written form, the author’s responsibilities are also:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To use the templates provided by the WP/WU in charge of communication; ● To verify that referenced and annexed documents have been approved and released; ● To ensure the correct identification of documents;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To store the electronic document native files (and on-line copies) of any final versions of documents in the project’s document repository; To update documents with the appropriate signatures when approved. <p>A guide to the formal drafting of the RESILIENCE deliverables is offered in Annex 1 to this document.</p>
Reviewer	<p>Reviewers are individuals who have sufficient knowledge to assess the deliverable’s contents. The reviewer’s responsibilities may vary according to the type of review being conducted, be it scientific or technical. The goals of the reviewer’s activities are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure correctness, completeness, consistency, and accuracy of the deliverables; Support individual staff and teams in the preparation of the deliverable and enhance their insight into the work they do and the processes they apply; Advise the staff and teams for the construction of a correct base for the next phase of development of the project and/or deliverable; Increase the deliverable quality; Advise staff and teams on how to work on the deliverable with more efficiency, providing information on the state of art and experts to involve;
Approvers	<p>For the GA n. 101079792 deliverables, the Board of Directors (BoD) members are responsible for the final approval. Before approval, they may consult with individuals without executive responsibilities but with expertise in a specific domain.</p> <p>After approval and submission, REA may send remarks and requests regarding the deliverables. In this case, the BoD should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate REA’s remarks and requests; In collaboration with the PC, send a request to the author(s) asking for corrections or modifications to the deliverable, and for a new review process. <p>For deliverables that are not indicated in the GA, any member of an advisory/management body or WP team can be an approver.</p>

3.2 Processes

3.2.1 Prepare the deliverable

What	A new deliverable is prepared by the author(s).
Start	When a new deliverable must be created
Roles involved	Author(s)
Result	First draft of deliverable prepared
Notes	The author shall take care to ensure that the deliverable is compliant with the project’s requirements (e.g. adopts RESILIENCE PPP templates, RESILIENCE Data Management Plan, CC-BY license)

	In case of a document, it receives the status "DRAFT and the change history of the document reports it as "Initial draft"
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3.2.2 Review of the deliverable

What	All deliverables are sent by the author(s) to the reviewers 45 days prior to the submission deadline. Reviewers have 15 days to submit their revision to the author(s) Author(s) have 7 days to correct the text in case of minor revisions; 15 days in case of major revisions Board of Directors has 7 days to approve the text.
Start	When the deliverable has been prepared
Roles involved	Author(s), Reviewer(s)
Result	List of remarks, requests for modifications and correction proposals to be brought to the deliverable. In case of a document, it maintains the status "DRAFT" and the change history of the document reports it as "Revised text"
Notes	All deliverables that are in the form of document may also be subject to a language quality review.

3.2.3 Correction of the document

What	Based on a list of remarks, requests for modifications and correction proposals, the author brings the necessary modifications to the document.
Start	When reviewers or BoD ask for modifications or corrections
Roles involved	Author(s)
Result	Document reviewed and corrected, ready to be verified The document maintains the status "DRAFT"

3.2.4 Verification of the deliverable

What	[For the GA n. 101079792 deliverables only] This is a formal quality check to reduce non-conformity of the deliverable with conventions, standards, guidelines, and quality criteria, as well as to verify formal aspects (identification, conventions, etc.). The check is finalised in 1 day.
Start	After the review, before submitting the document to Approval group
Roles involved	Author(s), PC
Result	Deliverable verified by the PC In case the deliverable is not conformant, defects are transmitted to the author(s) and corrections are brought to the deliverable. The deliverable status does not change. In the case of a document, verification date is indicated on the cover.

3.2.5 Approval of the deliverable

What	<p>[For the GA n. 101079792 deliverables only]</p> <p>In this process the deliverable is reviewed by the Board of Directors. A review form or a specific collaborative tool with reviewing features shall be used to collect comments from the BoD.</p> <p>In the case of a document, changes and comments are tracked directly. Approval time is set to 5 working days. If the Board of Directors needs advice from experts, approval time may be extended to a maximum of one month. At the end of the time set for the approval, the approval group decides to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Accept the deliverable with no changes. ● Accept the deliverable with minor corrections. ● Reject the deliverable <p>The Executive Director shall notify his/her decision by email to the author of the deliverable (WP and WU leaders are copied). In case of a document, if the document is approved, the PC adds the approval date on the cover. PC uploads the deliverable on the EC webportal.</p>
Start	Once the deliverable is verified
Roles involved	Author(s), BoD, PC
Result	<p>Deliverable accepted, accepted with corrections, or rejected. In the case of a document, the information about the status of this document is updated in the change history.</p> <p>If approved, in the case of a document, it receives the status "FINAL" and approval date is indicated on the cover.</p>
Notes	A maximum of two approval cycles should be considered as acceptable.

3.2.6 Delivery

What	<p>[For the GA n. 101079792 deliverables only]</p> <p>The PC delivers the document to REA by uploading the document onto the EC webplatform and on Zenodo. The PC informs the WP Leader or body chairman.</p>
Start	The document has been verified and is ready to be delivered
Roles involved	PC
Result	Conclusion of the process

3.3 Quality assurance

All deliverables produced in the scope of the RESILIENCE PPP must comply with the following quality criteria.

Type of deliverable	Quality criterion	Description
Document	Appropriate content for intended audience	The document is clearly written with its audience in mind, their skills and job responsibilities. The document's physical form is appropriate for the audience's work environment.
Document	Availability	The document is available to all readers at the agreed-upon time (A final delivery date has been defined before the document preparation, considering internal and external dependencies and resource availability)
Document	Cleanliness	The document is legible on paper/screen. The document is free of typographical, grammatical, and formatting errors.
Document	Completeness	No needed information is missing.
Document	Compliance with contractual requirements	The document complies with the objectives, standards and specifications included (or defined by reference) in the agreed-on requirements (whether the Grant Agreement, specific contracts, or work statement)
Document	Compliance with EC document standards	Appropriate, recommended, or required documentation standards have been used.
Document	Consistency	The document does not contradict itself in either content or style. All terms have the same meaning throughout the document and within documents of which it forms a part. All items and concepts are referred to by the same name or description throughout the document. The level of detail and presentation style is consistent throughout the document.
Document	Correctness	The document contains no erroneous information.
Document	Readability	Use of generally accepted rules of English grammar, capitalization, punctuation, symbols, and notation. Non-standard terms, phrases, acronyms, and abbreviations are defined. The information presented is logically organized. The level of complexity is appropriate to the intended audience.

4 Risk management provisions

4.1 Overview

Consistent and active monitoring of risks and opportunities is essential for a successful rolling out of the project’s activities. The level of risk within the WPs may be consistently contained and reduced by identifying risks and monitoring them regularly.

Risk management is considered as an integral part of the WP management process. To build a common risk and opportunities management framework within RESILIENCE PPP and between RESILIENCE PPP and REA, the methodology described herein is applied.

4.2 The proposed Risk Management Model

For a risk management strategy not to be solely reactive (actions put into place only when the risk occurs: implemented directly to manage emergencies), or if preventive, not just based on looking for the “most likely” risks, a real risk prevention strategy must be adopted.

The following image describes the approach adopted.

Figure 1: Summary of the Risk Management Process

4.3 Risk Management Process

Following the above model, the next sections describe the steps that the EB, the PC and WP Leaders follow in handling risks.

4.3.1 Risks identification

The identification of risks is a systematic attempt to specify the threats to the WP planned activities. Risk identification must take into consideration the WP activities that will be influenced by any risk.

Once identified, all risks shall be listed and described in the Critical Risks register included in the European Commission webportal dedicated to the continuous reporting of the RESILIENCE PPP.

4.3.2 Risks escalation procedure

The risks escalation procedure has three levels:

1. WP level: the risks are collected and recorded in the recurrent WP Team meeting minutes, their ratings are agreed with the WP Team Leader, their mitigation is appropriately followed up;
2. PC level: the risks with high Residual Risk level, after mitigation, are examined, eventually re-rated and followed up;
3. Executive Board level: the risks with a persistent Residual Risk level and likely to endanger the GA business are discussed and effective mitigation strategy is established.

4.3.3 Risk Mitigation

During the EB meetings and the WP/WU monthly progress meetings, the mitigation actions are identified, and mitigation strategies are agreed on to further implementation. Mitigation actions are monitored during the same meetings.

5 RESILIENCE PPP key performance indicators

RESILIENCE assesses the quality of the outcome and output of its activities according to measurable Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

The following table defines the key performance indicators for all the WPs. KPIs are both quantitative and qualitative. A certain degree of flexibility is possible on a case-by-case basis, and only with the prior explicit agreement of the Executive Director.

For the PPP, KPIs are monitored at each Reporting Period and during the monitoring activities conducted by the Board of Directors (including Annual reviews).

WP	Task	KPI	Notes
1	Meet other RIs	# of meetings; # of events created by resilience for partnering; # of partners contacted and engaged; # initiatives of other RIs to which RESILIENCE is invited to join/collaborate	Formal and informal meetings; meetings aiming at one-to-one and collective exchange; advice purposes
1	Meet other RIs	# of RIs met	Meetings with representatives and members; advice purposes
1	Engagement of the Italian Ministry representative	# of meetings	Formal and informal meetings
1	Engagement with national representatives for ERICs	# of meetings	Formal and informal meetings
1	Creation, discussion and GenA approval of the draft of the RESILIENCE ERIC statutes, bylaws and protocols	Construction of the stakeholders' platform by 06/2024 # of meetings with stakeholders	Success relies on a roadmap shared and accomplished by WP leaders, PC, BoD, GenA
1	Development of the business model and financial plan	# of meetings; # of experts involved in the creation; # expert reviews	Main aim should be effective long-term sustainability
1	Support to the applications for political and financial support of RESILIENCE partners	#of requests of support/requests satisfied by WP team members	-
1	Support to the applications for political and financial	Success of presented application	Performance analysis is based on the evaluation reports received by competent authorities/organizations

	support of RESILIENCE partners		
1	Establish connections with the national research infrastructures in the partner countries	# of coordinated activities; scientific/economic/strategic impact of coordinated activities	Self-assessment; evaluation conducted by Advisory Board Members
2	Service catalogue creation	#workshops to review service catalogue; #services evaluated; service prioritisation	Formal and informal meetings; self-assessment; quality of catalogue is also assessed according to the user requirements as indicated by WP3 Users
2	IT Services	#IT Services evaluated; IT Service prioritisation; #IT Services implemented	Formal and informal meetings; self-assessment
2	Data Management Services	#DM Services evaluated and establishment of prioritisation	Formal and informal meetings; self-assessment
2	Data Management Plan	#workshops to review DMP	Formal and informal meetings; self-assessment
2	TNA activities	#TNA calls; # TNA scholars; #TNA hosts TNA full-cycle management	TNA evaluation board review; self-assessment; feedback collection from TNA scholars and hosts
2	Training Services activities	#Training resources evaluated; #workshops to evaluate trainings; Development of Training Service Management Plan	Formal and informal meetings; expert reviews; quality is also assessed according to the needs of WP3 Users
3	Users requirements, Use cases, User stories	# of focus group meetings	Self-assessment; quality of collected information is also assessed according to the needs of WP2 in service development
3	Users requirements, Use cases, User stories	# interviews conducted and transcribed	Self-assessment; quality of collected information is also assessed according to the needs of WP2 in service development
	Users requirements, Use cases, User stories	Quality of interviews' structure, conduction, outcome	Checked against WP3 user survey quality criteria (see below) via self-assessment and by using evaluation forms for interviewees and interviewers.
3	Users requirements	# of user requirements mapping for service prioritization	Self-assessment; quality of collected information is also assessed according to the needs of WP2 in service development
3	User stories	# of user stories	
4	Update and implement the RESILIENCE C&D	# of website unique visitors, sessions per month, views per month, social media	

	Plan, facilitate, stimulate and monitor the activities planned	followers and subscribers; # of social media posts and engagements; # of participants to events; # of newsletter subscriptions	
4	Define the differentiated strategy to reach out to the RESILIENCE users archetypes and especially to scholars	# of website unique visitors, sessions per month, views per month, social media followers and subscribers; # of social media posts and engagements; # of participants to events; # of newsletter subscriptions	Assessment is based on the users archetypes; attention is paid to scholars
4	Exploit the network of the ReIReS TNA grantholders to gain insights on how to (better) communicate the results of the RESILIENCE TNA Programme	# of positive reactions by TNA Hosts after a call for TNA host institutions; # of new TNA Hosts (institution, archive, or library); # of posts on RESILIENCE social media accounts; # of applications by researchers after a call for TNA fellowships	
6	Monitoring	#of completed monitoring activities	Budget and effort are monitored every six months; the project’s development is monitored every month by the SCC and every six months in bi-lateral meetings between the ED and the WP/WU leaders
6	Submission of deliverables	# deliverables submitted	-
6	Deliverables quality check	Application of the review process to each deliverable	Review is assigned to reviewers who know RESILIENCE and are experts in the topic presented by the deliverable

5.1 KPI monitoring process

This process describes how the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) are monitored. The process entails a periodic review meeting, to discuss performance level and all metrics (KPI and quality indicators) and whether they are conforming to the targets and objectives. If not, determine the root cause of the problems, propose solutions to meet or exceed the performance level and quality requirements and implement improvements.

During the PPP, the review meeting is held during the monitoring activities conducted by the Board of Directors (including Annual reviews). Current initiatives and progress in improving individual situations are also covered during this review meeting.

The roles and responsibilities are:

- **Executive Director (ED):** The ED monitors and reports on KPIs.
- **Executive Board of Directors (EB):** receives information on a regular basis
- **WP Leaders:** escalate the issues that impact the defined WP Performance Indicators

The input for the process is the KPI measurements for the period covered.

The following tasks must be performed:

- Step 1 – Identify all KPI deviations

Roles	Project Coordinator
What	PC makes the list of all deviations of the KPI values against the targets set

- Step 2 – Root causes analysis of the deviations

Roles	WP Leader
What	WP leader identifies the root causes of deviations based on a thorough analysis of the current and past values and plan specific initiatives to address them. KPI improvement initiatives should focus on strengthening business fundamentals without losing sight of cost efficiency and responsiveness.

- Step 3 – Define and follow-up Performance level improvement actions

Roles	Project Coordinator and WP Leader
What	Based on the root causes analysis, the WP Leader and the PC define and plan a series of Performance level improvements actions to address the major causes and correct the deviations. Performance level improvement action plan should focus on strengthening quality and performance level without losing sight of cost efficiency and responsiveness of the actions. The Performance level improvement actions must be implemented and followed-up according to the agreed plan.

- Step 4 – Performance Indicators Management review (on request)

Roles	Project Coordinator and WP Leader
What	On request of Project Coordinator, Performance Indicators Management reviews may occur during the monthly WP progress meeting with persons responsible for measuring and providing defined performance levels (WP Leaders and the Project Coordinator). The purpose of the meeting is to review performance of the measured performance level (KPI), KPIs adjustment (also according to the agile approach adopted by the whole project and/or by WPs and WUs) and improvement actions follow-up.

	<p>Each meeting should have a defined agenda that includes a review of measured performance levels for the given period, a review of improvement initiatives defined, current performance level metrics.</p> <p>A discussion of what improvements are needed based on the current set of metrics.</p> <p>Meeting minutes are produced.</p>
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6 Continuous improvement of the project: how do we ensure it?

6.1 Reviews

According to D8.1, RESILIENCE Governance, HR Policy and Management and Access Policy, resulted from the RESILIENCE project (Grant Agreement no. 871127), RESILIENCE evaluates its activities through an Annual Review Process, which is put in place once the ERIC is established (§2.4.3.3 Annual review process):

The annual reviews serve to evaluate the activities of the past year and to plan the activities of the upcoming year and should take place 4-6 months before the end of each year. Each partner shall draft an individual report, following a template by the SO. The Unit chairs shall condense the individual reports into Unit reports. The Board of Executive Directors shall combine the Unit reports into a periodic report including a discussion of Key Performance Indicators. The Board of Executive Directors drafts recommendations for the strategy of the upcoming year under consultation of all governance bodies. The review process shall follow an iterative approach in gathering and integrating the feedback from all governance bodies in order to get an agreed-upon set of recommendations. Members of the Advisory Board offer advice on the draft to the Assembly. The Board of Executive Directors finalises the annual report including a publishable summary and a financial report.

Moreover, according to §2.4.3.4 Evaluation,

A comprehensive evaluation of the RI shall take place every 4 to 6 years with 4 years at the earliest and 6 years at the latest. The aim is (1) to assess if strategic goals and settings have been implemented and (2) for the evaluators to provide feedback on the planned strategy for the upcoming 4-6 years. For this purpose, the Board of Directors appoints external evaluators.

A list of members of the Advisory Board is prepared by the General Assembly and confirmed by the Board of Executive Directors (§2.4.2.6). A definitive list for the Preparatory Phase is expected to be presented at the General Assembly on July 13th, 2023. However, the board is conceived as an inclusive body, which is modified according to the needs of advice of RESILIENCE on scientific, strategic, technical, financial, legal, operational issues.

For the Preparatory Phase, while monitoring activities are implemented at least every six months and at the time of the reporting periods established by the GA n. 101079792, comprehensive reviews are planned to take place in the three months after the conclusion of the evaluation for the Reporting Period 1 and as a parallel activity of the preparation of the documentation for Reporting Period 2.

6.2 Surveys

RESILIENCE makes use of two surveys to ensure the continuous improvement of its activities and check on the quality of the actions, initiatives, and strategies it puts in place for its user communities: the User Survey and Events ex-post survey.

While the formulation of these surveys may change over time, according to the evolution of technology, lessons learned and specific information RESILIENCE may need to collect for e.g. statistics, their formulation remains guided by the following criteria.

a) User survey

RESILIENCE focuses on the users' needs, so user requirements are surveyed comprehensively as possible. A 2-phased guide for focus groups with experienced participants from the various fields of Religious Studies is already available. The first phase is a semi-structured guideline-single-Interview, where the participants are asked about their research, the RIs available to them and the expectations they have from RESILIENCE. The second phase consists of a group discussion to find out about the needs of the future users and of the possibilities and advantages of the future RI by using synergy effects of a group dynamic.

The criteria that guide their formulation are:

- Openness: the interview consists of thematically ordered but openly posed question complexes, structured by underlying themes of interest, which initially build on what has been said and can later inquire about new aspects. The transition between the question complexes is deliberately open and gently formulated to have a narrative-generating effect;
- Specificity: exact follow-up questions to what has been said are asked if a point has been hinted at but not intensively explored. Following what has been said, the interviewer can specifically inquire further through immanent questions, without already uncovering new facts. The follow-up questions are based on what the interviewee has said. The guideline differs between "Introductory Question", "Specification Question" and "Key Question". The sequence should be: "open" question at the beginning, "specific" and/or "key question" afterwards;
- Contextuality: questions should be asked in such a way that the subjective and/or institutional relevance of the interviewee is mapped - also with regard to the social and institutional context of the interviewee;
- Comparability: to analyse meaningful theses from the various interviews conducted, it must be possible to compare them in terms of content. Therefore, the interviews are semi-structured. This approach takes into account all mentioned criteria, but also ensures comparability;
- Validity: The strategy of triangulation increases the validity of the interview's content. This does not only include openness to the use of the approach of mixed methods to enrich the qualitative studies with quantitative ones, but as well the data- and researcher triangulation, which is achieved through the variation of the different focus groups.

b) Events feedback survey

RESILIENCE WP₄ - Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation adopts an agile approach and therefore makes use of the online surveys to collect feedback after RESILIENCE events (lessons, workshops, webinars, meetings, etc.) when it is logistically feasible, WP/WU leaders request so, and the activity may be reiterated. This approach allows an efficient effort allocation while ensuring that the feedback information is collected after those activities that the organisers identify as strategic. The feedback is shared with the organizers of the subsequent event and with the wider group of the WP leaders and the Service Coordination Committee for their insight.

The criteria that guide their formulation are:

- Goal oriented: the goals for the attendant are defined in advance by all the people involved in the making of the event and checked via the form. Goals are balanced according to the community

- needs, the development of the RI, and the phase it is going through. They are both topic-specific (e.g. teaching about the challenges and opportunities of DataScience in Theology and Religious Studies or the basics of scraping and analyzing data from the internet) or RESILIENCE-centered (e.g. offering a clear insight into RESILIENCE/into how RESILIENCE can support me in doing research);
- Collaboration: the Communication officer/team presents a draft of the form to the event organizer for possible additions or improvements. The form is adopted when there is agreement on the text;
 - Measurability: the level of appreciation is synthetically measured in quantitative and/or qualitative terms;
 - Openness: submitters have the possibility to comment on their choices and to come with general feedback;
 - Adaptability: the evaluation form can be adapted towards the type of event;
 - Standardization: some elements are always included in the form, allowing the possibility to compare and give an overview of the results of the different events;
 - Completeness: the survey collects feedback on the event both as a process and as a product.

6.3 The RESILIENCE Compass

Additionally, as a result of two workshops which took place between January and February 2023, RESILIENCE adopted a common compass to be adopted as a guide for its activities and as an additional monitoring qualitative tool. The compass identifies the core elements of the Project Vision, lists the Ecosystemic Opportunities that the RI is engaging with, summarises the RIs design principles and clearly expresses the values on which RESILIENCE structures its mission.

Figure 2: The RESILIENCE Compass

7 Control of the QAP

7.1 Follow-up Activities

The QAP is a living document which is updated at least yearly to take account of new information and changed requirements. The Project Coordinator is in charge to revise and update the QAP as appropriate.

The Project Coordinator is responsible for the follow-up of the QAP prescriptions during the whole WP.

8 Annex 1. How to shape your deliverable. The case of a document

8.1 Templates

Standard formats and templates have been established for most types of documents and standard WP applications, such as Word and Excel.

The templates are available in the project's repository on Google Drive.

8.2 Document Structure

The main characteristics of document design are outlined in the following sections. New document templates created for a WP or a body shall be prepared in compliance with the design described here.

8.3 Cover page

All documents must have a cover page which identifies the WP, the document, author, date of production, type of document, intended recipients, and quality-assurance information.

More precisely, each document must have a cover page containing:

- The header or footer with the European flag
- document title
- author(s) of the document, accompanied with their institution's name into brackets
- document name as described in the initial RESILIENCE Data Management Plan, available on the project's repository on Google Drive;
- version and the revision number of the document
- date of the last revision
- document status

The document should also include a revision table (change history) containing, for each revision:

- revision number of the document itself
- revision date
- object of the revision,
- status of the document (e.g. Draft)

8.4 Page header and footer

Moreover, on each page:

- document title and subject
- status of the document
- version and the revision number of the document
- page number

8.5 Table of contents

Documents more than 3 pages long must be divided into chapters with each chapter structured into sections and sub-sections.

A contents page must be produced and included in the document after the cover page listing these chapters, sections and sub-sections. A consistent numbering scheme for chapters, sections and sub-sections must be used and chapters must be individually page-numbered (the page number must be chapter-page to facilitate document changes, so that individual chapters may be replaced without the need to reprint the entire document).

The documents more than 5 pages long must have a separate page with a table containing the chapters and sections with their page numbers.

8.6 Tables and Figures

Figures and tables must be included within the text rather than grouped at the end. They must be numbered consecutively, for example 'Figure 1', 'Figure 2' or 'Table 1', 'Table 2', and so on. Table headings must be placed above tables, with figure captions centred beneath figures.

8.7 Reference Information

If a document contains a lot of detailed reference information, it must contain a comprehensive index for easy reference. When the tool allows it, references to other parts of the document must be dynamic, using cross-reference features.

8.8 Glossary

When a document is intended for a wide spectrum of readers, who may have differing vocabularies, it must clearly and briefly define its terms, expressions, and acronyms. The listed terms, expressions and acronyms must be sorted alphabetically. The glossary must be located at the end of the document, as the first appendix.

8.9 Document Properties

Whenever possible and to allow automated desktop processing, the documents must contain the following Summary properties:

- Title
- Subject
- Author, accompanied of the institution's name

As custom attributes, the following must also be included:

- Document ID
- Status
- Reviewed by
- Role of verifier
- Verification date
- Approval leader name
- Acceptance Validation date

8.10 Date specification

To keep uniformity in all documents produced for this WP and to allow standardised searching by file-name pattern, the format used for the specification of a date should be as much as possible the following:

dd/mm/yyyy

8.11 File formats

Documents are stored in two different electronic formats:

- **As native files** created with a text-processing application and editable with this application, for example MS-Word.
- **As on-line copies (PDF)**, converted from the native files, and suitable for viewing and printing on a variety of computer platforms. On-line copies cannot be edited.

When required, authors are also expected to provide hardcopies of documents.

8.12 Document Security

The need for document security varies according to the scale, sensitivity, and importance of the information and activities supported by the document. The security measures outlined below shall be followed

8.13 Confidentiality

The document author is responsible for setting the level of document confidentiality based on the following list of confidentiality levels:

- Confidential: restricted circulation, only for documents concerning contractual matters
- Public: no restrictions on circulation

8.14 Virus Control

Virus detection and prevention measures and appropriate user awareness procedures must be implemented for all documents.

9 Applicable Documents

Applicable documents are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement, although they are not repeated in the present document.

ID	Date	Title/Reference
A1	28/08/2022	Grant Agreement n. 101079792
A2	29/11/2022	Consortium agreement based on the DESCA – Model Consortium Agreement for Horizon Europe, version 1, December 2021

10 Reference Documents

Reference documents are intended to provide background and supplementary information.

ID	Date	Title/Reference
R1	21/10/2021	D8.1 RESILIENCE Governance, HR Policy and management and Access Policy (RESILIENCE 2YSEP GA n. 871127)
R2	12/12/2022	RESILIENCE PPP DMP, Initial draft, RESILIENCE_WP6_RESILIENCE PPP DMP_00.01_DRAFT, available at https://docs.google.com/document/d/1imPNaKXwLUc4uux3IRPOZBHaHa2oqAhT/edit
R3	18/11/2022	D6.2 Templates and guidelines for the monitoring, reporting and management activities, which is a public document available on the RESILIENCE website.

11 Revision Log

ID	Date	Nature of Revision	Approved by
R1	22/05/2023	From version 00.01 to 00.02: Update of KPIs, insertion of reference to Compass, other minor revisions, editing	

Funded by
the European Union